

DSSC QUYOSH ELEMENTLARI VA ULARNING TAYYORLANISH USULLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada bo'yoq bilan sezgirlashtirilgan quyosh elementlari (DSSC)ning ishlash prinsipi, tuzilishi, tayyorlash usullari va amaliy qo'llanishi tahlil qilinadi. DSSC texnologiyasining asosiy afzalliklari — arzonligi, tayyorlash jarayonining soddaligi, past yorug'lik sharoitida ham samarali ishlashi va ekologik tozaligi ilmiy asoslar bilan yoritiladi. Shuningdek, nanostrukturalangan materiallardan foydalanish, barqaror bo'yoqlarni ishlab chiqish va qattiq elektrolitlarni joriy etish orqali samaradorlikni oshirish imkoniyatlari hamda istiqbolli qo'llanish yo'nalishlari batafsil tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar. Quyosh elementlari, DSSC, bo'yoq bilan sezgirlashtirilgan batareyalar, nanomateriallar, energiya samaradorligi, qayta tiklanadigan energiya, elektrolitlar, fotovoltaika.

СОЛНЕЧНЫЕ ЭЛЕМЕНТЫ DSSC И СПОСОБЫ ИХ ИЗГОТОВЛЕНИЯ

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассмотрены принцип работы, структура, методы изготовления и практическое применение солнечных элементов, чувствительных к красителю (DSSC). Подробно анализируются основные преимущества технологии DSSC — низкая стоимость производства, простота изготовления, высокая эффективность при низкой освещённости и экологическая чистота. Также освещаются перспективы повышения эффективности за счёт использования наноструктурированных материалов,

стабильных красителей и твёрдых электролитов, а также возможности применения DSSC в различных сферах.

***Ключевые слова.** Солнечные элементы, DSSC, сенсibilизированные красителями батареи, наноматериалы, энергоэффективность, возобновляемая энергия, электролиты, фотовольтаика.*

DSSC SOLAR CELLS AND METHODS OF PREPARATION THEREOF

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***Annotation.** This article analyzes the operating principle, structure, fabrication methods, and practical applications of dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs). The key advantages of DSSC technology — low production cost, simple fabrication process, high efficiency under low-light conditions, and environmental friendliness — are discussed based on scientific evidence. In addition, the prospects of improving efficiency through the use of nanostructured materials, stable dyes, and solid-state electrolytes, as well as the potential applications of DSSCs in various fields, are comprehensively reviewed.*

***Keywords.** Solar cells, DSSC, dye-sensitized batteries, nanomaterials, energy efficiency, renewable energy, electrolytes, photovoltaics.*

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electrolytes, as well as the potential applications of DSSCs in various fields, are comprehensively reviewed.

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Introduction. Throughout human history, energy sources have been one of the main factors in the development of society. In ancient times, man used energy as a simple mechanical force - by lighting a fire, operating windmills and water mills, but in modern times, energy has deeply penetrated all aspects of life. Today, it is impossible to imagine industry, transport, communications, medicine, information technology and everyday life without energy[1].

Since the second half of the 20th century, the global demand for energy has increased dramatically. Population growth, urbanization, and technological developments have increased pressure on traditional energy sources - coal, oil, and natural gas. As a result, environmental problems related to energy supply, global warming, atmospheric pollution, and depletion of natural resources have become urgent issues[2]. Therefore, the development of clean and sustainable energy technologies such as renewable energy sources - solar, wind, biomass, geothermal, and hydropower - is considered an important scientific and practical direction today. One of them, solar energy, is of particular importance as an environmentally friendly, unlimited, and sustainable energy source. In particular, one of the new methods of using solar energy - dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSC) - is gaining attention due to its low cost, relatively simple preparation, and the possibility of achieving high efficiency.

Research methodology. This study analyzes the role of energy sources in human life and provides detailed information about the structure, operating principle and preparation methods of DSSC technology[3].

In nature, energy sources are divided into two main groups: non-renewable energy sources (coal, oil, natural gas and radioactive substances) and renewable energy sources (solar, wind, hydro, bioenergy, geothermal sources)[4].

Renewable energy sources are characterized by their environmental friendliness, safety and inexhaustibility. The most effective and reliable of them is solar energy. Solar cells are used to convert solar energy into electricity. Currently, there are first, second and third generation technologies, among which DSSC (Dye-sensitized Solar Cell) technology is distinguished by its low cost, simplicity of the preparation process and environmental friendliness[5].

Solar energy is widely used as a clean, safe and inexhaustible source. Today, there are three generations of solar cells:

The first generation - photovoltaic elements based on monocrystalline and polycrystalline silicon.

The second generation is thin-film solar cells (based on a-Si, CdTe, CIGS).

The third generation is elements based on nanostructures: DSSC, organic and perovskite solar cells.

DSSC are highly sensitive dye solar cells, consisting of the following main components:

1. Transparent electrically conductive glass (FTO or ITO) – transmits light to the maximum extent and provides electrical conductivity.
2. Photoanode (TiO₂ nanostructure) – converts light energy into electrons.
3. Photosensitive dye – absorbs photons and generates electrons.
4. Electrolyte – carries out the process of electron recovery.
5. Counter electrode (Pt or graphite) – a layer that carries electrons.

As a result of this structure, sunlight is converted into electricity by the DSSC.

DSSC preparation technology:

1. Preparation of a transparent electrically conductive surface

FTO (fluorine doped tin oxide) windows are often used. They are prepared based on fluorine and tin oxide solutions, grown by spraying on the surface of the window, and then polished.

2. Preparation of the photoanode

The photoanode is made from TiO₂ nanocrystals. To do this, TiO₂ powder is mixed with distilled water, acetic acid, and PEG to make a paste. The paste is coated on the FTO surface and then heated at 450°C.

3. Preparation of the electrolyte

The electrolyte is prepared based on a polymer. KI or TPAI salts are dissolved in a DMSO solution, then PVP and PMMA polymers are added to form a gel.

4. Preparation of the photosensitive dye

The dye is obtained from natural sources: extracts are prepared from spinach, red onion peel, red cabbage, flower petals, and fruits. The leaves are dried and ground into a powder, then mixed with ethanol and filtered.

5. Cathode preparation

A platinum solution is dropped onto the FTO glass and heated in a muffle furnace at 450°C, then washed with ethanol[6].

Literature review. There are different types of solar cells, including silicon-based photovoltaic cells, inorganic-flow cells, organic solar cells, and dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs). DSSC technology was first introduced by Michael Grätzel in 1991 and has attracted attention due to its simple fabrication method, low cost, and flexibility[7]. Prospects for DSSC technology. Creation of flexible solar cells based

on plastic substrates, increasing efficiency up to 20% by optimizing dyes and electrolytes, developing elements that operate stably under the influence of temperature and ultraviolet light, and combining DSSC elements with other renewable energy technologies[8].

DSSC applications include:

- phone chargers, small gadgets;
- power-generating windows in buildings;
- low-power sensor power supply;
- as a cheap energy source in remote areas.

In the future, DSSC technology is expected to be widely used in powering devices, developing smart windows and devices. However, research is ongoing to improve efficiency and ensure stability[9].

Conclusion. Dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSC) are widely recognized as a promising direction in renewable energy technologies. This technology is distinguished from other photovoltaic systems by its simple manufacturing process, the possibility of using cheap raw materials, and its environmental friendliness.

The analysis shows that the main advantages of DSSC devices are: relative simplicity of preparation, the ability to work on flexible substrates, the ability to make elements of various colors and transparency, and high efficiency even in low light conditions. Although the efficiency has been achieved in laboratory conditions up to 14–15%, research is ongoing to increase this indicator and ensure stability at the commercialization stage. Thus, DSSC technology has great potential for the production of cheap, stable, and efficient solar cells. Future research should focus on increasing efficiency, strengthening stability, improving scaling technologies, and developing “green” synthesis methods with minimal environmental impact. This creates a broad opportunity for the global development of DSSC technology not only as an object of scientific research, but also as a practical source of energy production.

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